

Corporate Social Responsibility and Earnings Quality of Listed Nigerian Companies

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Abstract

Despite the growing importance of corporate social responsibility (CSR) in business operations, there remains a lack of consensus regarding the relationship between CSR and earnings quality. While some studies suggest that CSR initiatives can improve the accuracy and reliability of a company's financial statements, others have argued that such initiatives may be used to deflect attention away from underlying financial problems, potentially compromising the quality of a company's earnings. This lack of clarity has important implications for investors, regulators, and other stakeholders, as they seek to understand the true economic performance of companies and make informed decisions about whether to invest, regulate, or otherwise engage with them. The event of corporate scandals and the current failure of significant corporate organisations in the United States of America (USA), Germany, China, and Nigeria, which is highly rated in financial misappropriation, have been crucial in highlighting the critical role of earnings quality in corporate institutions and expanding understanding of the concept of "earnings quality." The study focused on the relationship between corporate social responsibility and the earnings quality of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Ex-post facto study design was used in this study to gather information from the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE). The sample for this study consists of all manufacturing firms listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE). Out of the twenty (20) consumer goods companies, a total of ten (10) were chosen; the sample technique employed for this study was the purposive method. This will assist the researcher better understand the research questions and ensure that specific population features are emphasised. The sample size for this study was made up of the chosen companies, and several quoted consumer products companies were excluded because they were not yet listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange in 2010, the study's base year (NSE). This makes a total of one hundred and twenty observations that will be applied in the panel data analysis. Purposive sampling technique was used for this study. The research revealed that hypothesis one shows a positive relationship of community relations on earning persistence (EP). This is indicated by the sign coefficient that $\beta_1 = 4.415 > 0$. This result is consistent with the a priori expectation as it was expected that community relations will have a positive relationship on earning persistence, hypothesis two shows that employee relations (ER) has a negative (-8.864) effect on discretionary accruals (DA). This is indicated by the sign coefficient that $\beta = (-8.864) < 0$. This shows that a 1% increase in employee relations will lead to 8.8% decrease discretionary accruals. This result is inconsistent with the a priori expectation as it was expected that the employee relations will have a positive effect on its discretionary accrual, hypothesis three findings demonstrates a negative correlation between corporate social responsibility and earning quality (EQ). This shows model three's negative coefficient from is not significant. This finding revealed an increment in corporate social responsibility which led to a reduction in earning quality due to real activities in firm earnings manipulation. Therefore, to sustain positive impact of CSR on earning quality in this study, real activities on firm manipulation must be suspended on the listed companies. On the basis of the research recommends a increase corporate social responsibility, there must be transparency in information disclosure to maintain a reliable earnings persistence, avoidance of firm manipulation of earnings must be consistency, Management are to develop a sustainable activities to portray a good image of the company.

Keywords: Corporate social responsibility, Earnings quality, Earnings persistence, Discretionary accruals, Community relation, Employee relation

Background to the study

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) is an increasingly important topic for companies across the globe. It refers to the commitment of businesses to operate in a way that is socially responsible and sustainable, taking into account their impact on the environment, society, and the economy. The concept of CSR is closely linked to the notion of earnings quality, as companies that engage in socially responsible practices are often perceived as more trustworthy and more likely to generate high-quality earnings (Sodiq, 2022).

Earnings quality is a measure of the accuracy and reliability of a company's financial statements. High-quality earnings are those that are not artificially inflated by accounting tricks or other manipulations, but instead reflect the true economic performance of the company (Babatunde et al., 2015). This is important for investors, as it allows them to make informed decisions about whether to invest in a company or not.

CSR influences earnings quality by improving the reputation of the company. Companies that engage in socially responsible practices are often viewed more favorably by investors, customers, and other stakeholders (Litov, 2019). This can translate into increased demand for the company's products or services, as well as a lower cost of capital. In turn, this can help to improve the quality of the company's earnings, as it becomes less likely that the company will engage in questionable accounting practices in order to meet earnings targets.

However, it is important to note that there is also a potential downside to CSR when it comes to earnings quality. In some cases, companies may engage in CSR initiatives as a way of deflecting attention away from other, less positive aspects of their operations (Habbash & Haddad, 2020). This can create a situation in which the company's reputation is improved, but the underlying financial performance of the company is not necessarily any better. In such cases, the quality of the company's earnings may still be compromised, as the company may engage in accounting practices that are designed to mask underlying problems.

Earning quality still remains a controversial topic in light of the unethical behaviours of companies that have resulted in numerous corporate failures (Chinwe & Obehioye, 2021). The corporate world has encountered numerous problems with financial reporting that have led to accounting scandals and corporate failures in the United States of America (USA).

In Nigeria, a few numbers of firms were reported predators of fraudulent acts. The firms were indicted for submitting counterfeited financial report. An instance of this could be traced back to 2018 with Nigeria Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC) in retrospect. According to their yearly statistics, there were 44.4% more fraud instances in 2018 than there were in 2017, going from 26,182 to 37,817 (Ololade et al., 2020).

This obligation is a social responsibility that can gauge how much the business is conscious of growing in a way that improves the environment (Irestaluna, 2020). The success of every business is tied to its adaptability and flexibility to the environment within which it executes its functions (Adeyemi & Asaolu, 2015). For instance, with changes in the government policies and COVID-19 outbreak, the business needs to adapt itself with the new policies and even the COVID-19 pandemic which resulted in social distancing and consequently lock down having a negative effect on the business market.

Statement of the problem

Over the years, numerous business firms that have consistently displayed unethical social responsibility behaviour have linked examples of misappropriation of earnings to fraudulent scandals. Rajogopal and Venkatachalam's (2015) study looked into the 2002 failure of well-known corporations like WorldCom and Tyco International and found that they were notorious participants in scandalous acts like accounting fraud, earnings management, fraudulent accounting, and unethical corporate social responsibility. The senior management of the two businesses used earning quality but failed to immediately report instances of losses. Instead, they altered the outcome to their own benefit, hiding their subpar services and operational efficiency. The study, therefore, highlighted the urgent need to further examine the quality of financial reports and improve regulatory polices globally. Similarly, Choi and Pae (2015) noted that the fraudulent cases, mentioned above, stemmed from an integration of manipulative actions by the companies' management, thus producing a system of abuse to the ethics of financial reporting.

When discussing the 2002 case of WorldCom and Tyco International, Cobert and Wheeler (2018) used a similar tone. They also discovered that the two businesses had concealed their

deceitful behaviour under the guise of favourable social criticism as part of their CSR strategy. They were simultaneously preparing their financial reports using discretionary accruals while concurrently hiding reports of losses as they materialized. They presented phony and excessive profit statistics in place of real loss records in order to project a favourable image to the public, especially on Wall Street. The senior managements were rewarded for their ability to forecast figures that turned out to match the result expected, and they ensured the practice remained in that manner in order to keep their accolades afloat. Thus, the companies' financial records of earnings persisted increasingly year in, year out.

CSR involves taking ethical and voluntary actions to improve the well-being of society, the environment, and stakeholders (Erah & Ikhu-Omoregbe, 2017). Community relations and employee relations are two important aspects of CSR. By engaging in activities that benefit the community and treating employees fairly, a company can build strong relationships with stakeholders and improve its earnings quality. The relationship between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and earnings quality of a company has been a topic of interest for many researchers. Specifically, the impact of CSR on earnings persistence and discretionary accruals has been a subject of debate. While some studies suggest that CSR can enhance earnings quality by reducing the likelihood of earnings manipulation and increasing earnings persistence, others argue that CSR may distract managers from focusing on financial performance and lead to increased discretionary accruals (Tribo 2018).

Therefore, the problem at hand is to investigate the relationship between CSR (employee relations and community relation) and earnings quality of companies as regards earnings persistence and discretionary accruals. This problem is important because earnings quality is a key determinant of investor confidence and trust in financial reporting, and CSR has become an increasingly important aspect of corporate strategy and reputation. Understanding the relationship between CSR and earnings quality can help investors, policymakers, and managers make informed decisions regarding the trade-offs between social responsibility and financial performance. It is very important to note that there is a dearth of knowledge as regards this.

Objectives of the study

Examining how corporate social responsibility affects the earnings quality of the listed Nigerian manufacturing companies is the primary goal of this research project.

Consequently, the study specifically seeks to:

- i. Determine the relationship between community relations and earnings persistence of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.
- ii. Investigate the effect of employee relations on discretionary accruals of Nigerian manufacturing companies listed.
- iii. Ascertain if there is a significant relationship between corporate social responsibility and earnings quality of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Research questions

The following research questions was raised and answered to guide this study:

- i. What is the relationship between community relations and earnings persistence of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria?
- ii. Investigate the effect of employee relations on discretionary accruals of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.
- iii. Is there any significant relationship between corporate social responsibility and earnings quality of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were investigated at a significance level of 0.05 in an effort to address the research questions and in accordance with the study's objectives.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between community relations and earnings persistence of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Employee relations have no significant effect on discretionary accruals of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

H₀₃: Corporate social responsibility has no significant relationship with earnings quality of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Literature review

Conceptual review

Earnings quality

The quality of the earnings is one of the most crucial aspects of financial statements. It aids in performance projection and offers an accurate depiction of current performance (Rula, 2019). There have been numerous attempts in academia to elucidate the meaning of earnings quality. According to Alfred (2019), one of the key characteristics of a reliable financial report system is earnings quality. According to popular consensus, strong returns have a good effect on capital market efficiency and draw in a lot of investors and shareholders who are eager for accurate financial accounting information. In order to increase the quality of earnings through unheard-of changes in management, auditing, and corporate governance, those who create financial statements are focused on developing accounting standards.

Earnings quality measures

According to Petro and Alfred, an important component of financial reporting is the quality of the earnings (2015). Included in this is the criterion that financial reporting offers investors and other financial firms' trustworthy information for making financial decisions. Since high quality is an abstract idea, different people have different interpretations of it. Despite the lack of a standard, the literature has been able to define a number of substitutes for income quality based on specific criteria for what is deemed to be income quality. The purpose of this study is to identify the number of measures that truly contribute to the relevance of financial reporting decisions. For the objectives of this study, the following metrics have been identified and used to assess the quality of earnings.

Earnings persistence

The concept of earnings persistence indicates a recurrence of revenue. Earnings persistence is an indicator of income sustainability of earnings, according to a study by Vincent (2015). According to other studies, one of the factors affecting earnings quality is earnings persistence, which is defined as a return to the present value of future value. Earnings persistence was defined by Festus and Ademola (2020) as the capacity of reported earnings to exhibit durability and consistency over the long run. Long-lasting earnings are considered more sustainable and therefore tend to be of higher quality. The persistence of earnings can, thus, be deployed as the slope coefficient Θ_{it} in a first-order autoregressive model of current earnings to delayed earnings:

$$\text{Earnings}_{it} = \Theta_{0i} + \Theta_{1i}\text{Earnings}_{it-1} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Interpretation: The indices i and t represent the attribute and the year correspondingly. Θ_{1i} closer to 1 indicates higher persistence, while values closer to 0 indicate very short-term performance or poor persistence.

Discretionary Accruals

According to Hasan and Ahmen (2015), the preferred choice for conducting a metric analysis of discretionary accruals is the modified Jones Model (1991) pursuant to the statements of Dechow and Schrand (2010). Unlike other existing models, earnings will be accepted equally in this study.

$$\text{TACC} = \text{NI} - \text{OCF}$$

$$\text{TACC}_{it}/A_{it-1} = \alpha_t [1/A_{it-1}] + \alpha_{1i} [(\Delta\text{REV} - \Delta\text{REC})/A_{it-1}] + \alpha_{2i} [\text{PPE}_{it}/A_{it}] + \epsilon_{it}$$

$$\text{DA}_{it} = \text{TACC}_{it}/A_{it} - \alpha_t [1/A_{it-1}] + \alpha_{1i} [(\square\text{REV} - \square\text{REC})/A_{it-1}] + \alpha_{2i} [\text{PPE}_{it}/A_{it-1}]$$

Where;

TACC is total accruals

TACC is total accruals in firm i period t

NI is Net Income

OCF is earnings before taxation and extraordinary items and cash flow from operating activities

Δ REV is change in revenue

Δ REC is change in receivables

PPE is property, plant and equipment

t is residuals

A_{it} is Total assets in firm i period t .

A_{it-1} is Total assets in previous year.

Interpretation: Due to the predominance of earnings manipulation, the quality of income decreases as the value of the voluntary contribution increases, and vice versa.

Corporate social responsibility (CSR)

According to Irestaluna (2020), CSR is the state in which a person or company can take care of and react promptly and accurately to the circumstances surrounding them. The generated response has a great impact on the image of the company, and a good response inevitably improves the company's performance. CSR or corporate social responsibility is a term that refers to a concept with three basic components: economic, social, and environmental. These three areas are concentrated on producing a company's profit (economic) and empowering employees, communities (human or social), and preserving nature or the planet (earth and its environment).

Corporate social responsibility measures

The Kinder, Lydenberg, and Domini (KLD) scale, created in 1989 by Peter Kinder, Steve Lydenberg, and Amy Domini, is the most widely used CSR scale. This study also makes use of the KLD model. Zhangfan, William, and Tatiana (2016) claim that the KLD database gathers reliable CSR figures from a variety of sources, such as data from corporate governments, NGO data and more than 14,000 global media sources. The KLD index is utilised for conducting a metric analysis of the by CSRs, grouped using binary numbers (1's and 0's). A cell is designed as a 0 if no strength or weakness is discovered in a specific observation, and a 1 is apportioned to a cell given that there is a strength problem. This research report will, therefore, focus on community relations and employee relations.

Community relations

According to Maimunah (2019), a community is generally defined as a group of people who are permanently connected who live close and are interdependent to share a common goal and meet specific needs. Basically, community service involves charitable donations or support, for example, through which business encourage economic growth and development - efforts to enhance local infrastructure, community engagement, well-being, safety, health, and community education.

Employee relations

Employee relations, focuses on a range of challenges that employees encounter at work, such as industrial relations, personal and professional conflicts, health and safety, discrimination, and harassment. Researchers claim that CSR practices positively influence behaviours and attitudes at work. Research on this topic demonstrates the fact that CSR is significantly linked to employee engagement, and scholars have found that CSR results in a more satisfying work experience, and employee engagement is associated with CSR because employees take more pride in their organisation.

Theoretical framework

The main theory on which this work is presented is stakeholder theory. The theory was propounded by Edward Freeman in 1984. He defined stakeholders as groups and individuals who benefit from or are harmed by, and whose rights are violated or respected by corporate actions. According to

Yousf et al. (2015), the stakeholder theory offers a useful framework for examining how earnings quality and corporate social responsibility are related. According to the stakeholder theory, CSR is thought to be required for a corporation to achieve more extensive standards of responsibility through informing pertinent stakeholders (Babatunde et al., 2015).

Stakeholder theory focuses on the people and organisations that have an influence over or may have an impact on the organisation, as well as how these people and organisations will interact with the organisation. Stakeholder theory will be used for the purposes of this study to acknowledge and take into account the significance of each stakeholder group as a tactic to maximise long-term returns on investment for sustainable business success. It is a foreign paradigm, understanding of business strategy. Managers who want their business to stay successful must strategically focus on the requirements of their stakeholders because they control the resources needed to sustain an organization (Gras-Gil et al., 2016). The key concept of this strategy is that CSR may be a managerial competency that encourages more efficient resource management, which can improve earning quality (Orlitzky et al., 2003). Transparent financial reporting, demonstrates how important it is for decision-makers to receive information from the company's stakeholders.

Empirical review

Numerous studies have been done to look at how corporate social responsibility affects earnings quality, and some of the findings have implications for earnings quality. The results that may result from certain investigations include:

Corporate social responsibility and earnings persistence

Nguyen et al. (2022) conducted an exhaustive study on the impact of corporate social responsibility disclosure on the profitability sustainability of Vietnamese listed companies. The data was collected from 76 companies that disclosed financial statements, annual reports, and social responsibility of corporations and SOEs on the Vietnamese stock market between 2014 and 2017. In this study, correlations were estimated using the Generalised Method of Moments (GMM) regression method. The data obtained show that CSR has a positive effect on earnings persistence. This study helps to review previous studies on the relationship between CSR disclosure and earnings persistence in developing countries. The study also points out several policy implications for regulators and businesses with respect to transparency of disclosure to enhance corporate social responsibility through the preservation of earnings persistence.

Zhangfan et al. (2016) concluded that high CSR in their study progressively improved the quality of earnings compared to the manipulation of actual activities, indicating that the higher the CSR performance of a firm, the less likely it is that the firm is manipulating profits. The outcomes of real earnings management reinforce the evidence of transparent financial reporting by correlating with existing literature that suggests high CSR values prevent firms from participating in actual activity manipulation. According to Patricia and Catherine (2004), managers typically prefer very persistent earnings because this quality might boost their credibility with analysts and investors. Petro and Alfred (2015) believe that sustainability ascertains the value at which recent returns are maintained or repeated in the future. Persistence is considered an essential feature of revenues as it improves the accuracy of revenue forecasting. Persistence is projected primarily as a component of delayed income, such as cash flow and accruals, or the slope of the current income regression to delayed income. Higher sustainability is positively associated with high return quality as if represents. CSR standards are positively correlated with high accounting quality of companies that claim to have this, and the disclosure of truthful and fair financial returns is very important for CSR because it gives outsiders a foundation for and confidence in the company and its operations. Enhancing CSR and disclosure raises the standard of financial reporting, this raises financial accountability and transparency. Consistent, actionable and low volatility return process. It is highly appreciated by most investors (Li, 2018).

Corporate social responsibility and discretionary accruals

Siegel (2019) observed that the estimated level of discretionary accrual is perceived as a lower quality indicator of income. Litov (2019) argued that changing the recognition of accrual of cash flows could make financial statements more useful for representing a firm's performance. Similarly, Scholtens et al. (2013) was interested in determining whether the impact of accruals genuinely enhances the quality of revenue making financial statements more useful to user. Riahi-Belkaoui (2004) argued in his study that firms with higher discretionary accruals. Hsiangtsai et al. (2015) have studied financial report quality and CSR, and have shown that companies with good CSR performance can improve the quality of financial reporting by reducing the use of discretionary accruals. This means that socially responsible companies are not involved in the use of discretionary accruals that ultimately affect the quality of their earnings.

Sun et al. (2016) stated that some managers may exercise discretion over reported income to maximise profits. Although revenue management can be driven reasons other than accrual estimation errors, the revenue quality indicator is least dependent on valuation methods and thus provides a reasonably clear indicator of earning quality. Similarly, recalculations are expected to be associated with errors in accrual valuations as most recalculations affect accrual accounts. This claim is supported by Rahim (2015), who found that the majority of window dressings occur as a result of executive judgment and evaluation, in their study. Therefore, earnings management activities are viewed as opportunistic practices in which managers degrade the quality of reported revenues by inflating revenues in order to achieve budgetary goals in order to increase their rewards. Guidry et al. (2009) found that the managers also have an incentive to report low returns. This can be done by deferring earning when it is difficult to meet revenue targets for a particular year, or by offering a "big bath" for restructuring.

In her study, Gyungmin (2015) looked into the connections between the earnings quality level, documentation of charitable contributions, and voluntary corporate social responsibility disclosure. Companies listed on the Korea Stock Exchange between 2004 and 2010 made up the sample.

Discretionary accruals were used as a proxy for measuring the quality of earnings. Businesses with higher levels of corporate gifts had less conservative accounting and higher levels of discretionary accruals, it was demonstrated. In their study, Abdullah et al. (2015) came to the same conclusion about the modified Jones model's use of total discretionary accrual as a gauge of the accuracy of financial reporting (earnings management), which allowed companies with strong CSR records to manipulate earnings through accrual. Ines and Ademola (2020), focused on whether corporate social responsibility disclosures affect the quality of Tunisians earnings, and found that companies have more social disclosures, more management discretion, and more accounting conservatism when it comes to financial reporting. As a result, firms that make corporate social disclosures tend to utilize earnings management (discretionary accruals) more actively and report fewer incidents, supporting the concept that the opportunistic financial reporting hypothesis is affected by corporate disclosures. Li F. (2018) study employed a small sample size of carefully chosen U.S. companies to examine the relationship between environmental initiatives and discretionary accruals. They come to the conclusion that environmentally conscientious businesses are investigated. Since you do not want to damage your company's reputation or run the risk of legal action, you do not meddle with your intention to import. Their findings further support the idea that businesses are less inclined to manage their earnings through discretionary accruals when they engage in environmentally friendly activities. Additionally, they contend that environmentally conscious businesses are less likely to turn for profit in an effort to improve their financial outcomes.

Susanto (2016) looked into the connection between CSR and earning quality and asserted that while there is a negative correlation between CSR and discretionary accruals in the enterprise,

an increase in the tendency to invest in or report on CSR activities does not necessarily result in real change. Instead, it's likely that opportunism will be what drives this tendency. In order to give investors more open financial information, Kim et al. (2016) wanted to discover if CSR enterprises act differently while making accounting and operational decisions. They found that CSR organisations are less likely to manipulate actual activities and/or discretionary accruals in an effort to manipulate earnings. To uphold society's ethical standards, financial information needs to be more trustworthy and transparent.

Methodology

Research design

This study adopted an *ex-post facto* study plan to collect data from the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE). *Ex-post facto* refers to research that investigates possible casual relationships by observing existing situations or condition and finding plausible causal relationships in the past.

Population of the study

All of the manufacturing companies registered on the Nigerian Stock Exchange make up the population for this study (NSE). There were 45 manufacturing businesses listed on the NSE as of November 2021, with 20 of them coming under the consumer products category, 10 coming under the healthcare category, and 15 operating under the industrial goods category.

Table 1: Quoted manufacturing companies under NSE

S/No.	Quoted Manufacturing Companies	Number of Companies
1.	Consumer Goods	20
2.	Healthcare	10
3.	Industrial Goods	15
Total		45

Source: Nigerian Stock Exchange November, 2021

Sample size and sampling techniques

Out of the 20 consumer goods companies, a total of 10 were chosen; the sample technique employed for this study was the purposive method. This will assist the researcher better understand the research questions and ensure that specific population features are emphasised. The sample size for this study was made up of the chosen companies, and several quoted consumer products companies were excluded because they were not yet listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange in 2010, the study's base year (NSE). This makes a total of one hundred and twenty observations that will be applied in the panel data analysis.

Table 2: Sampled size for the quoted manufacturing companies

S/N	Company
1.	Nestle Nigeria Plc.
2.	Cadbury PLC
3.	Guinness Nigeria PLC
4.	Flour Mills Nigeria PLC
5.	Nigerian Brewery PLC
6.	PZ Cussons Nigeria PLC
7.	Nigerian Enamelware PLC
8.	Unilever Nigeria Plc.
9.	Honeywell Flour Mill Plc.
10.	Vitafoam Nigeria Plc

Source: Nigerian Stock Exchange November, 2021

Method of data collection

Secondary data from yearly reports published between 2010 and 2021 that were retrieved from the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) fact book was used in this study. The data in this audited financial report is considered suitable for this study as it has already been already certified by independent experts.

Method of data analysis

Multiple regression analysis and descriptive methods were used in this study's data analysis. On the basis of corporate social responsibility, descriptive statistics attempted to study the variation between the mean and standard deviation of the dependent variable. The Hausman test is utilised, and multiple regression is used (cross-section random effect). This is due to the fact that it enables researchers to gauge the strength of the relationships between the determined measures that will be applied to the testing of our variables.

The multiple regression formula is $Y_{it} = \alpha_0 + b_1X_{it} + b_2C_{it} + \dots + e_{it}$

Panel data were employed in this study because information on a specific individual or unit was gathered throughout a number of time periods. Over a twelve-year period (2010-2021), ten (10) listed manufacturing companies in the consumer goods industry were investigated.

Model specification

To examine the effect of corporate social responsibility on earnings quality, the following model was employed:

$$Y = f(X)$$

$$X = (x_1, x_2, x_3)$$

Where;

X = Independent Variable (Corporate Social Responsibility)

x₁ = Community Relations

x₂ = Employee Relations

x₃ = x₁, x₂

Where:

Y = Dependent Variable (Earnings Quality)

y₁ = Earnings Persistence,

y₂ = Discretionary Accruals,

y₃ = y₁, y₂

The simple equations are given as:

$$y_1 = f(x_1) \dots\dots eq1$$

$$y_2 = f(x_2) \dots\dots eq2$$

$$y_3 = f(x_3) \dots\dots eq3$$

The regression equations are given thus as:

$$y_1 = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \mu_i \dots\dots\dots eq1$$

$$y_2 = \alpha_0 + \beta_2 x_2 + \mu_i \dots\dots\dots eq2$$

$$y_3 = \alpha_0 + \beta_3 x_3 + \mu_i \dots\dots\dots eq3$$

Where: α_0 = constant or intercept of earnings quality, β = regression parameter, which measures the coefficient of corporate social responsibility μ_i = error term or stochastic variable.

Measurement of variables

The following proxies and regression models were used in this study to investigate corporate social responsibility and earnings quality.

Table 3: Measurement of variables

Variables	Abbreviations	Measurement	Source
Employee Relations	ER	The KLD CSR index score using dummy variables is used to calculate employee relationships. 1 indicates strength and 0 indicates weakness.	Wan & Muhammed (2016)
Community Relations	CR	The KLD CSR index using dummy variables is used to calculate community relationships. 1 indicates strength and 0 indicates weakness.	Kramer (2016).
Earning Persistence	EP	$Earnings_{it} = \Theta_0 + \Theta_1 Earnings_{it-1} + \epsilon_{it}$	Fanani (2012); Meliyanti & Nora (2019)
Discretionary Accruals	DA	$TACC = NI-OCF$ $TACC_{it}/A_{it-1} = \alpha_1 [1/A_{it-1}] + \alpha_{1i} [(\Delta REV - \Delta REC)/A_{it-1}] + \alpha_{2i} [PPE_{it}/A_{it}] + \epsilon_{it}$ $DA_{it} = TACC_{it}/A_{it} - \alpha_1 [1/A_{it-1}] + \alpha_{1i} [(\Delta REV - \Delta REC)/A_{it-1}] + \alpha_{2i} [PPE_{it}/A_{it-1}]$	Hassan & Ahmed (2015); Dechow & Schrand (2010)

Source: Researcher’s compilation (2022)

Descriptive analysis

In this section of the analysis, a summary of the data set is provided, and an attempt is made to describe its main features. The descriptive analysis of the panel data created through numerical representation is shown in Table 1 below, which shows the mean, maximum, minimum, and standard deviation of selected variables on corporate social responsibility measured by community relations (CR) and employee relations (ER). Earning quality is determined by earning persistence (EP).

A priori expectation

In this study, corporate social responsibility is expected to have a significant impact on the earnings quality. The table below illustrates the expectations according to the variables because this expectation is based on research findings from the literature. The a priori expectations of the model are expressed below as: $\alpha_i (i = 0, 1, 2) > 0; \mu = 0$.

Table 4: A-priori expectation

S/N	Models	A priori expectations IF:
1.	$y_1 = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \mu_i \dots\dots\dots eq1$	$p < 0.05; H_0$ was rejected. $\alpha > 0 \beta > 0$
2.	$y_2 = \alpha_0 + \beta_2 x_2 + \mu_i \dots\dots\dots eq2$	$p < 0.05; H_0$ was rejected. $\alpha > 0 \beta > 0$

3.	$y_3 = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 x_3 + \mu_i \dots \dots \text{eq2}$	$p < 0.05$; H_0 was rejected. $\alpha > 0$ $\beta > 0$
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Results and discussion

Descriptive analysis

Table 5: Descriptive statistics result

Variable	Companies	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
CR	10	.8896	.09615	.75	1.00
ER	10	.7800	.07118	.66	.83
DA	10	3.1230	1.91496	.08	6.97
EP	10	7.9920	6.97775	.28	19.98

Source: Researcher’s computation, 2022

*Observations: 120

Discussion

From the reported descriptive statistics in Table 3, community relation value of the sampled firms used is within the range of 0.75 and 1.00. This indicates that there is no wide gap between the minimum and maximum values of community relation within the quoted companies. The standard deviation of 0.09 is not too large compared to the mean of 0.88 and this suggests that there is a slim dispersion from the mean and the variable. This implies low volatility in predicting values of community relations within the selected ten companies for 12years. Therefore, this means that most manufacturing companies execute community relationship within the observed 12 years.

Employee relations (ER) reported a mean value of 0.78 and standard deviation of 0.07. The standard deviation measures the extent of dispersion from the mean. This is seen and confirmed from the difference and distances between the minimum and maximum values of 0.66 and 0.83 respectively and this implies low unpredictability. This means employee relationship service within the 12 years understudied were well implemented either by training or by welfarism as the mean values far from zero but close to one.

Discretionary accruals (DA) also reported a mean value of 3.12 and a standard deviation of 1.91. This confirms the high unpredictability as the difference between the minimum and maximum values of 0.08 and 6.97.

From the reported descriptive statistics, earning persistence shows a range between 0.28 and 19.98. This indicates that there is a wide gap between the minimum and maximum values of earning persistence. The standard deviation of 6.97 is too large from one compared to the mean value of 7.99 and this suggests that there is a wide dispersion from the mean and the variable which implies a high unpredictability for the observed period of years.

Inferential statistics

In order to determine the relationship between corporate social responsibility of community relations and employee relations on earnings quality measured by earnings persistence and discretionary accruals, the study regressed the measurements of each independent variable on the measurement of earnings quality (EQ) in linear regression and correlation analysis

Test of hypotheses

Test of model one

Research objective 1: Determine the relationship between community relations and earnings persistence of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Research question 1: What is the relationship between community relations and earnings persistence of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Research hypothesis 1 (H_{01}): There is no significant relationship between community relations and earnings persistence of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Following the selection of the most appropriate estimate method for hypothesis one, the estimation methods of ordinary least square (OLS), fixed effect, and random effect were used to conduct its

initial analysis. This influenced the post estimation tests that were used to determine the best estimation method for Model 1. The outcomes of the diagnostic tests performed on Model one are displayed in Table 6.

Table 6: Post estimation tests for model one

Tests	Statistics	Probability
Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian multiplier test for random effects	10.59	0.0006
Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity	39.20	0.0000
Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data	110366.036	0.0000

Source: Researcher's study, 2022

p<0.05

Discussion

The output of the model's analysis as well as the results of the diagnostic tests used to evaluate the selection and suitability of the estimating approach used are displayed in Table 6. To evaluate if the fixed effect, random effect, or pooled ordinary least square (OLS) estimate technique is appropriate for the model, the Hausman test was used. The random effect estimation technique is appropriate since the Hausman specification test's null hypothesis is that there is no systematic change in a model's coefficients. The Hausman test result showed that the fixed effect estimation method would not be suitable for this model. The study then conducted the Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian multiplier test to further evaluate the applicability of the random effect estimation method. The null hypothesis for this test is that a random effect is neither necessary nor acceptable for the model; the test's outcome showed a probability of 0.0006, which is below the 5% level of significance. The Hausman test result showed that the fixed effect estimation method would not be suitable for this model. The study then conducted the Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian multiplier test to further evaluate the applicability of the random effect estimation method. The null hypothesis for this test is that a random effect is neither necessary nor acceptable for the model; the test's outcome showed a probability of 0.0006, which is below the 5% level of significance. The result of the Hausman test indicated that the fixed effect estimation technique will not be appropriate for this model. The study then conducted the Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian multiplier test to further evaluate the applicability of the random effect estimation method. The null hypothesis for this test is that a random effect is neither necessary nor acceptable for the model; the test's outcome showed a probability of 0.0006, which is below the 5% level of significance. This indicated that the alternate hypothesis—random effect is suitable for the model—must be accepted since the study cannot accept the null hypothesis. Additionally, the heteroscedasticity of the residual variance was examined using the Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test. The test result showed a probability value of 0.0000, which is less than the 5% level of significance. The null hypothesis for this test is that the residual variance is constant. Inferring that the variance of the residual is not constant, this suggests that the study rejects the null hypothesis of constant variance. The Wooldridge test was used to check the panel data for autocorrelation. This test's result in this model indicated a probability value of 0.0000, which is lower than the 5% level of significance and has the null hypothesis that there is no first-order autocorrelation. However, it implies that the autocorrelation in the model indicates that the investigation rejects the null hypothesis.

Table 7: Regression analysis for model 1

Variable	Coefficient	Std Error	T	Probability
Community relations	4.415	25.611	0.172	0.867
Cons	4.064	22.903	0.177	0.864
F statistics	0.030			
Prob(f-statistics)	0.867			
R- correlation	0.061			

Dependent variable: EP; Obs: 120

p<0.05

Source: Researcher's study, 2022

$$EP_{it} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 CR_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

$$EP = 4.064 + 4.415 + \mu$$

Discussion

Hypothesis one tested the relationship between community relations and earning persistence of the quoted manufacturing companies listed on the Nigerian stock exchange, without bias to the fact that there exists other variables that may affect earning persistence. The result of the analysis on Table 7 shows a positive relationship of community relations on earning persistence (EP). This is indicated by the sign coefficient that $\beta_1 = 4.415 > 0$. This result is consistent with the *a priori* expectation as it was expected that community relations will have a positive relationship on earning persistence.

The positive coefficient of model one from Table 7 is insignificant. This is determined from the t-statistics result ($t=0.172$) which is less than the t-tabulated ($t=1.96$). This is further confirmed by the probability values of t-statistics ($p\text{-value}=0.865$) which is more than the 5% level of significance. We therefore infer from the result of this model that the relationship of community relations on earning persistence is positive but not significant.

The Rof 0.061 explains that only 6.1% of the total variation is explained by the independent variable while the balance of 93.9% is explained by factors outside this study.

Decision: This result is consistent with the *a priori* expectation of this model, though not significant. Thus, we have achieved the objective of this model, answered the question as well as tested the hypothesis.

Discussion

This study revealed a positive relationship of community relations on earning persistence (EP). The positive coefficient of model one from Table 7 is insignificant. This result is consistent with a study led by a significant correlation between contextual social disclosures and earning persistence was discovered by Ben and Halioui (2015). The claim made that an improvement in CSR performance and disclosure improves the quality of financial reporting, which has the knock-on effect of increasing financial transparency and accountability. This result was found consistent with the previous study, due to the trust and confidence provided to the outsiders through corporate social services with regards to the firms or companies.

Test of model two

Research objective 2: Investigate the effect of employee relations on discretionary accruals of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Research question 2: What is the effect of employee relations on discretionary accruals of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria?

Research Hypothesis H₀₂: Employee relations has no significant effect on discretionary accruals of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Ordinary least square (OLS), fixed effect, and random effect estimation approaches were used in the initial regression analysis of hypothesis two after the proper estimation methodology for it had been chosen. This is based on the decision made regarding the post estimation tests that were carried out while choosing the best estimation method for the models. The outcome of the diagnostic test is displayed in Table 8.

Table 8: Post estimation tests for model two

Tests	T-Statistics	Probability
Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian multiplier test for random effects	11.20	0.0004
Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity	0.59	0.4431
Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data	361179.937	0.0000

Source: Researcher’s study, 2022

$p < 0.05$

Discussion

The output of the model's regression as well as the results of the diagnostic tests used to assess the choice and suitability of the estimating technique used are displayed in Table 8. To evaluate if the fixed effect, random effect, or pooled ordinary least square (OLS) estimate technique is appropriate for the model, the Hausman test was used. The random effect estimation technique is appropriate since the Hausman specification test's null hypothesis is that there is no systematic change in a model's coefficients. The Hausman test result showed that the fixed effect estimation method would not be suitable for this model. The study then conducted the Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian multiplier test to further evaluate the applicability of the random effect estimation method. The result of this test indicated a probability of 0.00004, which is lower than the 5% level of significance. The null hypothesis of this test is that the random effect is neither necessary nor acceptable for the model. This demonstrated that the alternate hypothesis is random effect is suitable for the model must be accepted since the study cannot accept the null hypothesis. Additionally, the heteroscedasticity of the residual variance was examined using the Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test. The probability value for this test, which has a constant variance of the residual as its null hypothesis, was 0.4431, which is higher than the 5% level of significance.

This implies that the constant variance null hypotheses is according to which the variance of the residual is constant is accepted by the investigation. The Wooldridge test was used to check the panel data for autocorrelation. This test's result in this model indicated a probability value of 0.0000, which is lower than the 5% level of significance and has the null hypothesis that there is no first-order autocorrelation. However, it implies that the autocorrelation in the model indicates that the investigation rejects the null hypothesis.

Table 9: Regression analysis for model two

Variable	Coefficient	Std Error	T-statistic	Probability
Employee relations	-8.864	8.980	-0.987	0.353
Cons	10.037	7.031	1.428	0.191
F-statistics	0.974			
Prob(f-statistics)	0.353			
R ²	0.109			

Dependent variable: DA; Obs: 120

p>0.05

Source: Researcher's study, 2022

$$DA_{it} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 ER_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

$$DA = 10.037 - 8.864 + \mu$$

Discussion

Model two tested the effect of employee relations (ER) on the discretionary accruals of selected manufacturing companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE), without bias to the fact that there exists other variables that may affect discretionary accruals. The result of the regression analysis on Table 9 shows that employee relations (ER) has a negative (-8.864) effect on discretionary accruals (DA). This is indicated by the sign coefficient that $\beta = (-8.864) < 0$. This shows that a 1% increase in employee relations will lead to 8.8% decrease discretionary accruals. This result is inconsistent with the *a priori* expectation as it was expected that the employee relations will have a positive effect on its discretionary accrual.

The negative coefficient of model two is insignificant. This is determined from the t-statistics result (t=-0.98) which is less than the t-tabulated (t=1.96). This is further confirmed by the probability values of t-statistics (P-value=0.353) which is higher than the 5% level of significance. We therefore infer from the result of this model that the effect of employee relations on discretionary accruals is negative and insignificant.

The R² of 0.109 explains that 10.9% there is employee relation in discretionary accruals. The 89.1% explained by factors outside the study.

Decision: As a result of this model's statistical insignificance, the study will not be able to reject the null hypothesis, which states that there is no discernible impact of employee relations on

discretionary accruals, and will instead accept the alternative hypothesis. The outcome coefficient does not match the model's a priori prediction. As a result, we have accomplished the model's goal, provided an answer to the query, and validated the hypothesis.

Discussion of finding

This finding shows a negative (-8.864) effect of employee relations (ER) on discretionary accruals (DA). This is indicated by the sign coefficient that $\beta = (-8.864) < 0$. This shows that a 1% increase in employee relations will lead to 8.8% decrease discretionary accruals. Model two's negative coefficient is negligible. This finding conflicts with a study conducted by Seyede and Mohammed (2015) that used discretionary accruals to quantify earnings quality and found a substantial association between CSR and earnings quality.

According to Abdullah et al. (2015), who also came to the same conclusion in their study, firms with high CSR scores had a lower likelihood of manipulating earnings by using accruals. They used total discretionary accruals of the modified Jones model as a proxy for financial reporting quality (earnings management). This result were found contrary with the present study because most of the previous study concentrated more on earning management discretion which are less utilized or considered in the quoted manufacturing companies here in Nigeria.

Test of model three

Research objective 3: Ascertain if there is a significant relationship .between corporate social responsibility and earning quality of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Research question 3: What is the relationship between corporate social responsibility and earning quality of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria?

Research hypothesis H₀₃: Corporate social responsibility has no significant relationship with earnings quality of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Ordinary least square (OLS), fixed effect, and random effect estimation techniques were used in the initial regression analysis after the most acceptable estimation methodology for hypothesis three was chosen. This is based on the decision made regarding the post estimation tests that were carried out while choosing the best estimation method for the models. The outcome of the diagnostic test is displayed in Table 10.

Table 10: Post estimation tests for model three

Tests	T-Statistics	Probability
Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian multiplier test for random effects	9.03	0.0063
Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity	0.24	0.232
Wooldridge test for autocorrelation in panel data	1.435	0.027

Source: Researcher's study, 2022

p<0.05

Interpretation

The output of the model's regression as well as the results of the diagnostic tests used to assess the suitability of the estimating technique used is displayed in Table 10. To evaluate if the fixed effect, random effect, or pooled ordinary least square (OLS) estimate technique is appropriate for the model, the Hausman test was used. The random effect estimation technique is appropriate since the Hausman specification test's null hypothesis is that there is no systematic change in a model's coefficients. Additionally, the heteroscedasticity of the residual variance was examined using the Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test. The probability value for this test, which has a constant variance of the residual as its null hypothesis, was 0.232, which is higher than the 5% level of significance. This implies that the constant variance null hypothesis according to which the variance of the residual is constant is accepted by the investigation. The Wooldridge test was used to check the panel data for autocorrelation. This test's result in this model indicated a probability value of 0.027, which is less than the 5% level of significance and has the null hypothesis that there is no first-order autocorrelation. However, it implies that the autocorrelation in the model indicates that

the investigation rejects the null hypothesis.

Table 11: Regression analysis for model three

Variable	Coefficient	Std Error	T-statistic	Probability
CSR	-13.620	18.064	-0.754	0.472
Cons	33.855	30.274	1.118	0.296
F-statistics	0.568			
Prob(f-statistics)	0.472			
R	0.258			

Dependent variable: EQ; Obs: 120
 Source: Researcher's study, 2022

p>0.05

$$EQ_{it} = \alpha_0 + \beta CSR_{it} + \mu_{it}$$

$$EQ = 33.855 - 13.620 + \mu$$

Interpretation

Without bias against the existence of other factors that can influence earning quality, model three examined the strong association between corporate social responsibility and the quality of the earnings of quoted manufacturing companies listed on the Nigerian stock exchange. The examination of Table 11 findings demonstrates a negative correlation between corporate social responsibility and earning quality (EQ). The sign coefficient, which is = (-13.620) 0, indicates this.

This demonstrates that a 1% increase in CSR will result in a 13.6% reduction in earning quality.

As it was anticipated that corporate social responsibility would have a favourable association with earning quality, this finding does not meet the presumption. Model three's negative coefficient from Table 11 is not significant. The t-statistics result (t= -0.74), which is lower than the t-tabulated result (t=1.96), indicates this. Therefore, we conclude from the outcome of this model that there is a weak and unimportant negative correlation between corporate social responsibility and earning quality. The Rof 0.258 explains 25.8% relationship of corporate social responsibility with earnings quality. While the remaining 74.2% explained by factors outside the study.

Decision: As a result of this model's statistical insignificance, the study will not be able to reject the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant relationship between corporate social responsibility and earnings quality, and will instead accept the alternative hypothesis. The result coefficient does not match the model's a priori prediction.

Discussion of finding

The examination of Table 11 findings demonstrates a negative correlation between corporate social responsibility and earning quality (EQ). Model three's negative coefficient from Table is not significant. In contrast to a study led by Nguyen et al. (2022) who found a positive relationship between corporate social responsibility and earnings quality, the Kalle and Maria (2018) study found no relationship between corporate social responsibility and earnings quality. Wright and Ferris (2017) also found no relationship between corporate social responsibility and earnings persistence. According to a prior discovery, the variances from this conclusion could be due to variations in the types of industries.

Recommendation and conclusion

Summary of empirical findings

According to Hypothesis one, there was a 6.1% correlation between community involvement and continued income. Habbash et al. (2019), who claim that an improvement in CSR performance and disclosure raises the quality of financial reporting, which has the knock-on effect of raising financial transparency and accountability, backed up this finding.

In contrast to a study headed by Gyungmin (2015) that used discretionary accruals to gauge earnings quality and found a substantial link between CSR and earnings quality, hypothesis two

finds that employee relations had a negligible impact on discretionary accruals by 10.1%. Although Wright and Ferris (2017) asserted that there is a negative correlation between corporate social responsibility and earnings persistence, hypothesis three showed that corporate social responsibility were connected with earning quality by 25.8%.

Summary of theoretical findings

The theories reviewed from this study were stakeholders' theory, which posited that any manufacturing industry in Nigeria engaging in corporate social responsibility is doing so well and it is as a way of giving back to the society. They care not just about the company's owners (shareholders), but also about other stakeholders like the staff, the administration, and their host community. If the Nigerian manufacturing sector continues to support sustainability, they are predicted to eventually remain profitable and refrain from manipulating their earnings because sustainability efforts are anticipated to present a positive image of the business and draw in customers and investors.

Conclusion

This finding revealed an increment in corporate social responsibility which led to a reduction in earning quality due to real activities in firm earnings manipulation. However, if increment occurs in CSR and reduction exist in earning quality, this implies a high firm manipulation meanwhile a better a firm's CSR performance, the higher the earning quality, and the lesser is firm manipulation. Therefore, to sustain positive impact of CSR on earning quality in this study, real activities on firm manipulation must be suspended on the listed companies

Recommendations

On the basis of the study's conclusions, it is advised that:

- i) To increase corporate social responsibility, there must be transparency in information disclosure to maintain a reliable earnings Persistence.
- ii) Avoidance of firm manipulation of earnings must be consistency.
- iii) Management are to develop sustainable activities to portray a good image of the company

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